

Study of Properties of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Thin Films Prepared from Nanocrystalline Powder for Photovoltaic Application

*Dissertation Report Submitted
in
Partial Fulfillment for the Award of
The Degree of*

**MASTER OF ENGINEERING
[Metallurgical & Materials Engineering]**

With specialization in
Materials Technology

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Faculty of Technology and Engineering,
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Certificate

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled "*Study of Properties of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Thin Films Prepared from Nanocrystalline Powder for Photovoltaic Applications*" is submitted by Mr. Hamza H. Master in partial fulfillment of the *Master's Degree in Metallurgical Engineering in Material Technology* from the *Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara*. The present work has been carried out by him under my supervision and guidance. The matter presented in this dissertation has not been submitted for the award of any other degree or diploma.

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Abstract

The solar energy is converted to electricity using photovoltaic cells or solar cell concentrators. Research and development is carried out in this area since long time. Countries like European Union, Japan and United States have achieved significant success in photovoltaic technology using crystalline silicon solar cells. Nanotechnology in solar cells provides an opportunity to produce new materials, with high efficiency, low cost and simple manufacturing process.

Cu(InGa)Se₂ (CIGS) material used for absorber layer of a solar cell is group I-III-VI compound semiconductor material composed of Cu, In, Ga and Se. These materials possess band gap value in the range of 1.0 eV to 1.7 eV. It has absorption coefficient of the order of 10³cm⁻¹ at 1.5 eV and higher energy photons. Solar cells prepared from absorber layers of CIGS materials have shown an efficiency higher than 20%.

In this study we have synthesised Cu(In_(1-x)Ga_x)Se₂ nanocrystalline compound by high-energy ball milling. High-energy ball milling was carried out to prepare Cu(In_(1-x)Ga_x)Se₂ where x = 0.3 compound in a stoichiometric ratio of [1:0.7:0.3:2]. Milling was carried out in a planetary ball mill. Milled powder samples were collected at an interval of 30 minutes for X – Ray diffraction studies. X – Ray diffraction studies indicate chalcopyrite structure of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ compound.

Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ powder compound was deposited on a cleaned glass substrate to produce thin films of different thickness by flash evaporation technique. Scanning electron microscopy was done to study surface morphology of thin films. Absorption, transmission and band gap of thin films were obtained for optical characterization. Optical characterization shows that band gap increases with increase in film thickness. The resistivity of the thin films were measured by Vander Pauw technique. It was observed that resistivity ρ decreases with increase in film thickness.

Thus, it is possible to synthesize CIGS compound by high-energy ball milling. The thin films prepared from CIGS compound using flash evaporation technique shows desirable optical properties which can be used as CIGS thin film absorber layer in solar cells.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1 Introduction

Solar energy in terms of radiant light and heat from Sun has been harnessed by human since ancient times using a range of ever-evolving technologies. Solar energy technologies include solar heating, solar photovoltaic, solar thermal electricity and solar architecture which can make considerable contributions to solving some of the most urgent problems the world now faces. The earth receives 174 petawatts (PW) of incoming solar radiation (insolation) at the upper atmosphere. Approximately 30% is reflected back to space while the rest is absorbed by clouds, oceans and land masses. The spectrum of solar light at the earth's surface is mostly spread across the visible and near infrared ranges with a small part near to ultraviolet range. Sunlight absorbed by the oceans and land masses keeps the surface at an average temperature of 14°C. Photosynthesis carried out by green plants converts solar energy into chemical energy, this helps to produce food, wood and the biomass from which fossil fuels are derived.

Solar power is the conversion of sunlight into electricity, either directly using photovoltaic (PV) or indirectly using concentrated solar power (CSP). Photovoltaic converts light into electric current using the photoelectric effect. Solar cells (photovoltaic cells) produce direct current (DC) power, which fluctuates with the intensity of irradiated light. This DC power is converted to certain desired voltages or alternating current (AC) with the help of inverters. Multiple solar cells are connected inside the modules. Modules are wired together to form arrays and tied to inverter, which produces power with the desired voltage and frequency phase. Solar photovoltaic is growing at a rapid pace, although initially from a small scale to a total capacity of 67000 MW by the end of 2011. Thus, representing 0.5% of the world wide electricity demand.

Single crystal and polycrystalline silicon solar cells occupy an approximately 90% of current market for solar panels. This statistics are changing with rapid pace. Thin film solar cells like Cu(In,Ga)Se_2 (CIGS) and Amorphous Silicon are growing in demand as compared to Crystalline Silicon solar cells. The reasons for this are quiet

obvious, one it is easy to produce with large sizes and second it requires less material than crystalline silicon solar cells. CIGS is a group I – III – VI compound semiconductor material composed of copper, indium, gallium and selenium. The material is a solid solution of copper, indium and selenium (CIS) and copper, gallium and selenium with an empirical formula of $\text{Cu}(\text{In}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x})\text{Se}_2$ where $0 < x < 1$. CIGS is a compound with chalcopyrite structure and band gap value varies with composition x . When the value of x is 1 compound is CIS with band gap of 1.0 eV, and when x is 0 compound is CGS and band gap value increases to 1.7 eV. CIGS has an exceptionally high absorption coefficient of more than $10^5/\text{cm}$ for 1.5 eV and higher energy photons. CIGS solar cells with efficiencies greater than 20% have been claimed by National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) of United States.

Elemental compositions of thin film semiconductors are obtained by doping it with intrinsic defects. One of the simplest technologies of CIGS absorber layer deposition is by flash evaporation (FE) of nanocrystalline precursor compound. Thin film absorber produce by this technique will have uniform composition and good structural quality. FE is one of the most prominent techniques for the deposition of thin films of multi component alloys, whose constituents have different vapour pressures. This technique requires only one boat maintained at sufficiently high temperature to evaporate the least volatile component of the alloy. Even though fractionation occurs during the evaporation of each particle, it is so small that stratification in the film is limited to a few atomic layers. The net result of this simultaneous discrete evaporation is a vapour stream whose composition is uniform and identical to that of the source material. Accordingly, excellent control of film composition can be achieved.

CHAPTER 2

THEORY AND
LITERATURE REVIEW

2 Theory and Literature Review

SECTION I: High-energy Ball Milling for Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ Semiconductor Nanocrystalline Powder Formation

2.1 *Semiconductor Effect in Solar Cells* ^[1, 2]

“Photovoltaic” is the term used to represent the devices that generate electricity from sunlight. Solar cell or a photovoltaic device is usually semiconductor device which when exposed to sunlight creates an electron – hole pair. This electron – hole pairs should be as large as possible to obtain high efficiency of a solar module. These charge carriers that are separated must be at some electrostatic inhomogeneity for e.g. p – n junction, metal – semiconductor contact. Most important condition for charge carriers generated in solar cells is that, they must be mobile and in separated state. This condition should prevail until the time they reach to localized charge separating inhomogeneity.

As shown in Fig. 2.1 solar light is incident on the semiconductor material after passing through the ohmic contact. Most of the solar light will pass through Transparent Conducting Oxide (TCO) and n – type semiconductor layer and will be absorbed at p – type region. This layer is also referred as absorber layer.

Fig. - 2.1: Diagram of homojunction solar cells where incident photons creates an electron hole pairs in P – Type layers which are separated across P – N Junction

Fermi level is defined as the magnitude of energy required to remove an electron from a semiconductor into free space. In intrinsic materials, the Fermi level is approximately centered between the conduction band and the valence band. For n-type materials Fermi level is located towards conduction band and for p-type materials it is near to the valence band as shown in Fig. 2.2^[3].

Fig. – 2.2: Fermi Level Positions of p – type and n – type materials

At the p – n junction or charge separating inhomogeneity, electrons from n – side combines with holes from p – side, resulting into depletion layer or a space charge region (SCR). When a photon with energy greater than band gap of semiconductor, passes through the solar cell it will be absorbed by the material. This absorption takes the form of band to band electronic transition and thus an electron – hole pair is produced.

In order to create a charge flow through external load and effective energy generation, charge carriers should diffuse past the depletion region without recombining. This effect is known as photovoltaic effect. The current produce is termed as photocurrent as shown in Fig. 2.3.

Fig. – 2.3: Diagram of photocurrent generation with incident photons

2.2 Photon Absorption in Solar Cell Device

As it was mentioned in the previous article the result of photon absorption in a photovoltaic semiconductor is a generation of charge carriers. Direct band gap semiconductors utilize energy ' $h\nu$ ' incident from the photons to generate charge carriers, and these photon energies should be higher than the band gap E_g of semiconductor material. α is known as the absorption coefficient and it can be explained using the expression:

$$I(x) = I(0)e^{-\alpha x} \quad (2.1)$$

Where,

$I(x)$ is the light intensity at a depth x beneath the semiconductor surface and,

$I(0)$ is the intensity of light incident.

The expression for the absorption coefficient in a direct band gap semiconductor is given as,

$$\alpha = A(h\nu - E_g)^{1/2} \quad (2.2)$$

Where,

A is nearly constant in the wavelength range of interest in solar cells and depends on the refractive index of the semiconductor.

α is used to determine the thickness of the absorber layer required in a semiconductor. The thickness of an absorber can be taken as $2/\alpha$, where 90% of incident photons are absorbed by the layer. From equation 2 we can observe that the value of α increases with an increase in incident photon energy above E_g . Thus we get a clear absorption edge in a direct band gap semiconductor material.

In comparison to the above there is a certain class of semiconductors where absorption of a photon is accompanied by simultaneous creation of phonons. These semiconductors are known as indirect band gap semiconductors. The value of α in

indirect band gap semiconductor material depends on phonon energy E_p as well as $h\nu$ and E_g .

$$\alpha = \frac{B(h\nu - E_g + E_p)^2}{E_g^2 \left(e^{\frac{E_p}{kT}} - 1 \right)} \quad (2.3)$$

Where,

B is a constant.

The absorption edge in indirect band gap material is not as well defined as for direct band gap semiconductor. Some material can show both kinds of optical absorption characteristics at different photon energies. Germanium is a type of semiconductor which shows this behavior.

2.3 Classification of Solar Cells

Solar cell devices can be mainly classified into two types. First is based on macro and microstructure or degree of perfection of material, and another is on the basis of method of junction formation.

1.) a) Single Crystal:

This type of material is initially bulk materials which are cut into thin layer. These materials possess very high efficiency in comparison to other materials due to its crystal perfection (low loss situation). Cost of this material is relatively high due to difficulty in manufacturing and time consuming method of preparation. These materials are presently used in both concentrator and non – concentrator types of solar cells.

b) Polycrystalline:

This type of microstructure exists in both thin film as well as bulk material devices. Bulk material can be produced by casting, sintering, directional solidification, screen printing and simple melting. Polycrystalline thin films can be produced by evaporation, sputtering, ion – beam deposition or spraying. These devices are less expensive than single crystalline materials but they have low efficiency and stability due to inherent imperfections in the grain boundaries.

c) Amorphous:

This category of devices is exclusively made of thin films. These materials possess no short range order. The electronic and optical properties of these materials are different from polycrystalline or single crystal materials. These materials can turn out to be very cheap alternative for solar cells; however there are certain material and performance problems which are yet to be solved.

2.) a.) Homojunction:

Two semiconductors of same species (e.g. Si) are doped with different impurities (e.g. B and P) to obtain different majority carriers (p and n type). Such semiconductors when joined together (to form a junction) is called homojunction.

b.) Heterojunction:

This is the junction formed between p – type and n – type semiconductors of different species (e.g. CIGS and CdS).

c.) Metal Semiconductor/Schottky Barrier:

A rectifying contact made between metal and semiconductor is known as metal semiconductor or schottky barrier solar cell.

d.) Metal Insulator Semiconductor (MIS):

This type of semiconductor is formed by putting a thin insulating layer used to separate metal from semiconductor. Insulator is usually oxide semiconductor and its purpose is to increase output of device. Thickness of insulator is generally 10 – 30 Å.

e.) Semiconductor Insulator Semiconductor (SIS):

Metal is replaced from MIS semiconductor device by some degenerate semiconductor (e.g. Indium Tin Oxide ITO) to form SIS.

f.) Electrolyte:

Electrolyte in liquid form can be used to contact the semiconductor and provide necessary inhomogeneity. These types of solar cells are known as electrochemical cell.

2.4 *Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ as a Solar Cell Material*^[4]

The first CIGS solar cell was developed at Bell Laboratories in the U.S. in 1974 by evaporating CdS onto CuInSe₂ single crystals. Researchers have added gallium [Ga] to ordinary CuInSe₂ (CIS) to produce CuIn_(1-x)Ga_xSe₂ solar cells that have superior

energy conversion efficiency. CIGS solar cells have certain unique features over other thin – film silicon and cadmium telluride (CdTe) solar cells such as:

1. A high conversion efficiency comparable to polycrystalline silicon solar cells.
2. Endurance to photo degradation for long – term reliability.
3. Low cost.
4. High endurance to radiation.
5. Superior design.

CIGS also possesses other unique properties like:

1. Lattice defects that provide better control of the p – n junction.
 - ✓ High efficiency at 99.99% purity.
2. No carriers re – combination at crystal grain boundaries.
 - ✓ Small grain sizes that do not degrade cell performance.
3. Controllable band gaps.
 - ✓ Provide a double – graded band gap structure ideal for achieving high efficiency.
4. Higher light absorption coefficient than any other semiconductor.
 - ✓ Can generate sufficient electricity with a film thickness of 1 μm .
5. Addition of sodium increases carrier concentration.
 - ✓ Enhanced open circuit voltage and conversion efficiency.
6. Same thermal expansion coefficient as inexpensive soda lime glass.
 - ✓ Provides excellent film adhesion and serves as a source of sodium.

2.5 Role of Crystal Defects in Solar Cell Materials

Role of materials imperfection is very significant in study of material science. This knowledge will allow us to know material in terms of its physical, chemical, mechanical and electrical properties. One can choose to keep imperfection in a material in order to control certain properties, or to add certain properties like capacity to work under operating environment. There are various categories of materials used for solar cells and research is done on these materials to improve its performance and obtain high efficiency. Specific requirement involved in solar cell materials include collection, conversion, storage and transmission of energy from the sun.

The understanding of defect structure in chalcopyrite compounds of $\text{Cu}(\text{In,Ga})\text{Se}_2$ is important due to possible intrinsic defects and their contribution in deep recombination centers during performance of solar cells. Quaternary CIGS compound is a composite of many materials to obtain desired properties for specific function ^[5]. In such systems imperfection allowed to obtain one property may prove to be detrimental for some other. This requires careful and delicate variations in internal structure, and imperfections must be achieved through changes in crystal structure, chemical composition or both.

In chalcopyrite compounds point defects are occurring due to Cu vacancies and IIIcu anticite defects as they lead to Cu poor composition. Another defect is Se Vacancies, which makes a semiconductor n – type if Se is not supplied in excess during growth or annealing. Performance of CIGS material in solar cells is vastly dependent on these defects. These defects makes CIGS a heavy self compensated p – type semiconductor without any external doping. It also influences its electronic properties in such a way that carrier concentration and mobilities are Cu independent over a wide range ^[6]. Thus, effective control and modulation of defects in CIGS materials is necessary for improvement in performance of solar cells.

2.6 Nanotechnology and its Significance

Nanotechnology is closely related to nanoscience, the basic theoretical and experimental study of matter at the nanoscale, by applying the acquired knowledge for device manufacturing ^[7]. They are less known as basic technologies with a clear and distinct definition among the scientists, and recognized as interdisciplinary and cross sector research approaches. They are applied in various fields like electronics, optics, biotechnology or new materials, using effects and phenomena which are only found in the nano – cosmos ^[8]. Nanoeffects had been used since the middle ages, for instance in the red staining of church windows by finely distributed gold colloids or for the hardening of Damascene steel of sword blades by carbon nanotubes, without being aware of the physicochemical principles ^[8]. Physical properties of solid material such as electrical conductivity, magnetism, fluorescence, hardness or strength modify fundamentally with respect to the number and arrangement of the interacting atoms, ions and molecules.

Nanotechnology refers to the target – oriented technical utilization of objects and structures in a size range of 1 to 100 nm^[8]. Nanotechnology is an engineering with elementary unit of biological and inorganic nature i.e. atoms and molecules are arranged from small pieces to make a large object, which is known as “bottom up strategy”. On the other hand, tiny structures measuring only one thousandth of the diameter of single hair can be created by means of size reduction, which is called “top down strategy”.

Materials with microstructural features of nanometric dimensions are referred with various names in the literature such as nanocrystalline materials (a very generic term), nano crystals, nanostructured materials, nanophase materials, and nanometer sized crystalline solids or solid with nanometer sized microstructural features^[9]. Due to small size of grains a significant volume of the microstructure in nanocrystalline materials is composed of interfaces, mainly grain boundaries, i.e. a large volume fraction of the atoms resides in grain boundaries. Consequently, nanocrystalline materials exhibit properties that are considerably different from, and often improved in comparison to conventional coarse – grained polycrystalline materials.

2.6.1 Classification of Nanostructured Materials^[9]

Nanocrystalline materials can be classified into different categories depending on the number of dimensions in which the material has nanometer modulations. Three main categories of nanomaterials are:

- a.) Layered or Lamellar Structure
- b.) Filamentary Structure
- c.) Equiaxed Nanostructured Materials.

A layered or lamellar structure is a one dimensional (1D) nanostructure in which the magnitudes of length and width are much greater than the thickness that is only a few nanometers in size. Two dimensional (2D) rod – shaped nanostructure that can be termed filamentary and in this the length is considerably larger than the width or diameter, which are of nanometer dimensions. Among all the nanostructures most

common is equiaxed (all the three dimensions are of nanometer size) and are termed nanostructured crystallites.

2.6.2 Synthesis of Nano Crystalline Materials ^[9]

Table 2.1: Methods to synthesize nanocrystalline materials are as follows:

Starting Phase	Technique	Dimensionality of Product
Vapour	Inert gas condensation	3D
	Physical vapour deposition – evaporation and sputtering	1D
	Plasma processing	3D
	Chemical vapour condensation	3D, 2D
	Chemical reactions	3D
Liquid	Rapid Solidification	3D
	Electro deposition	1D, 3D
	Chemical reaction	3D
Solid	Mechanical Alloying / Milling	3D
	Devitrification of Amorphous phase	3D
	Spark erosion	3D
	Sliding wear	3D

2.6.3 Structure of Nanocrystalline Particles ^[9]

Two types of atoms can be distinguished: one is crystal atoms with nearest neighbor configuration corresponding to the lattice, and other is the boundary atoms with a variety of interatomic spacings, differing from boundary to boundary. Nanocrystalline metal contains typically a high number of interfaces ($\sim 6 \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-3}$ for a 10 nm grain size) with random orientation relationships, as a result substantial fraction of atom lies in the interfaces. Thus, nanocrystalline metals possess two structural components, the numerous small crystallites with long range order and different crystallographic orientations known as “Crystalline component”. Another is network of inter crystalline region, the structure of which differs from region to region; this will be referred to as the “interfacial component”. The interatomic spacings in the interfacial components have a wide distribution. In addition to it the

average atomic density is considerably less than the 'crystal density', depending on the type of chemical bonding between the atoms.

2.7 Nanotechnology for Solar Power Generation

The application of nanotechnology is regarded as an important factor for photovoltaics. It will achieve broad economic acceptance through considerable cost savings and increase in efficiency. This development is based on new materials and solar cell types with simpler production processes. Intersection of nanotechnology with energy is going to change the way it was hitherto being generated, stored, transmitted, distributed and managed ^[10]. Conventional solar cells have two main drawbacks: efficiencies and their expensive manufacturing cost. Efficiency of a solar cell depends on intensity of incoming photons with respect to band gap energy of solar cells. If the intensity of photon is less than the band gap energy it will pass through. If the incident photon energy is more than the band gap than this extra energy will be lost as heat. Thus, in order to utilize maximum of photon energy for power generation, the band gap should be properly designed for incident solar radiation.

Nanostructured layers in thin film solar cells offer three important advantages. First is due to multiple reflections, the effective optical path for absorption is much larger than the actual film thickness. Another advantage is that electrons and holes produced will have to travel over a much shorter path, and thus recombination losses are greatly reduced. As a result, the absorber layer thickness in nano – structured solar cells can be as thin as 150 nm, instead of several micrometers in the traditional thin film solar cells. Finally, the energy band gap of various layers can be made of the desired design value by varying the size of nano particles. This allows for more design flexibility in the absorber of solar cells.

2.7.1 Effect of Nanotechnology on Solar Cell Performance ^[11]

Solar cells at present cannot convert all the incoming photons into electricity because some of the photons can escape back out of the cell into air. Light in the ultra violet

region may be filtered out or get converted into damaging heat. This ultraviolet light could match with band gap of correctly sized nanoparticles and produce electricity. The difference of a few atoms between two quantum dots alters the band gap boundaries. Smaller nano crystals absorb shorter wavelengths or blue light, where as larger nanocrystals absorb longer wavelengths or red light. Changing the shape of the dot also changes the band gap energy level as shown in Fig. 2.4.

Fig. - 2.4: Relationship between size of quantum dots and incident light.

Furthermore, new material combinations such as polymeric semiconductors are increasingly used, although it possesses low conversion efficiency. This material could be produced much more economically in future, due to cheap mass production methods. The application of nanotechnological process such as plasma – aided procedures, design of surfaces and layer structures at the nano level, enables the optimization of cell structures and efficiencies of all solar cell types.

2.8 Introduction to High – Energy Milling ^[12]

Particle size reduction or comminution is an important step in many technological operations. High-energy milling is defined as the mechanical breakdown of solids into smaller particles without changing their state of segregation. This process is used to create particles of certain size and shape (including nanosize), to increase the surface area and induce defects in solids, which is desirable for subsequent operations such as chemical reactions, sorption etc. Milling not only increases the surface area of solids, but also increases the proportion of region with high activity at the surface.

Conventionally, the term fine milling is used for size range below 100 μm and the ultrafine milling for particles sizes less than 10 μm .

2.8.1 Milling Process ^[12]

Energy generation is the primary consideration for creating plastic deformation. To produce this energy the type of mechanical activation in high – energy milling is important. The main stress types applied during milling are compression, shear (attrition), impact (stroke) and impact (collision).

The multi – stage character of mechanical activation requires the application of high – energy mills with different working regimes. When using mills with application of balls as milling media, different motion of the balls can be observed as shown in Fig. 2.5. The motion can be described as cascading (A), falling or cataracting (B) and centrifugal (C).

Fig. - 2.5: Main Stress Types in Ball Milling; R1 – Compression, R2 – Shear (Attrition), R3 – Impact (Stroke), R4 – Impact (Collision)

2.8.2 Planetary Ball Mill

The planetary ball mill as shown in Fig. 2.6 owes its name to the planet – like movement of its vial. Since the vials and the supporting disc rotates in opposite direction, the centrifugal force alternately acts in like and opposite directions.

Fig. – 2.6: Movements of working parts and balls in a planetary mill

This force causes the milling balls to run down the inside wall of the vial which produces the friction effect. The material being milled and milling balls lifts and travels freely through the inner chamber of the vial and collides against the opposite inside wall [Suryanarayana 2001]. Planetary mills exploit the principle of centrifugal acceleration instead of gravitational acceleration. The enhancement of the forces acting on the ball in relation to the conventional ball mill is achieved by the combined action of two centrifugal fields. The charge inside vials performs two relative motions: a rotary motion around the mill axis and a planetary motion around the vial axis.

During the past decade, the problem of continuous feeding of a material into a planetary mill has been solved by novel planetary mills. These mills are of the industrial scale and operate in a continuous mode. In this mode the initial material is continuously fed into the mill. The coarser powder is returned for another cycle of milling and the final fine or nanoscale powder product is continuously provided as a result of the milling process. The productivity per unit volume of the working chamber for these mills is significantly higher (at least ten times) than that of conventional ball mills ^[12].

2.9 Variables of Planetary Ball Milling Process ^[13]

2.9.1 Speed of Rotation

The grinding action inside a mill is determined by the speed at which the mill cylinder is rotating. It is generally accepted that a speed that creates a cascading action of the media is most desirable. Cascading stage begins when the mill speed is such that the media charge breaks away from the mill wall at an angle of 45° to 60°.

2.9.2 Size of Grinding Media

The size of the grinding media to be employed is dependent on the milling conditions. Most effective grinding can be accomplished with the smallest media that can be used for milling. Smaller media offers more contact per mill revolution, resulting into uniformly fine – ground particles due to smaller voids. The size of the voids will fix the particle size that can exist, and assure more physical contact and decreases distance through which shear forces must act.

Larger media can produces greater impact energy followed by excessive heat in the mill, unless this energy is efficiently consumed during grinding action. This extra energy is useful for grinding large and tough particles or when the wet mixture is thixotropic.

2.9.3 Viscosity of Batch

The grinding of a solid in a liquid to reduce particle size or to make dispersion should be carried out at optimum consistency or viscosity, proportionate with the media size and density used. This is necessary to achieve maximum production yet keep media wear to reasonable rates such as 20% per year. If the viscosity is too high the grinding media will not have freedom of movement within the mill, but will cling together in a mass which rotates with the mill and produces no grinding action.

An increase in operating viscosity is necessary when a large diameter mill is considered. A heavier – bodied cushion is required to prevent wear due to greater media weight. Since more horsepower is needed to rotate a larger mill and as some of

this power is transformed into heat, some compensation is required for lowering the operating viscosity.

2.9.4 Amount of Grinding Media

Good practice calls for mills to be filled from 45 to 55% of the total volume. To minimize excessive ball and shell wear, full charges (50 to 55%) or charges no less than 45% are recommended. At values lower than 45% media tends to slip on the shell unless lifter bars are used.

2.9.5 Amounts of material to be ground

Usual practice for dry milling is generally carried out at material charge occupying 25% of the mill cylinder. This loading permits the grinding media (50% charge) to make effective contact with the material charge. The rule of thumb for wet milling is to fill the mill to about an inch over the media level. A minimum charge of 25% total mill volume should be maintained with good results obtained by filling the mill from 30 to 40% of its total volume.

Greater capacity at lower cost per unit mill load can be obtained if a high product charge is used, but at the cost of longer grinding time. Increasing the product charge results in longer milling time and decreasing the product charge reduces the milling time. Changing the amount could result in excessive temperature rise and increased media wear.

2.9.6 Wet Grinding & Dry Grinding

Wet grinding a material is generally slower than dry grinding. Dry grinding has a disadvantage of material packing up as it becomes finer, unless the fines are removed or a grinding aid is used. Another factor to consider in dry grinding is the problem of discharging the product. In order to collect the dry milled powder without removing the media, the mill must be rotated. Discharge housing must be used in this mill as it is rotated to discharge the product.

2.10 Mechanical Alloying of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Powder Compound

Powder mixture of pure metal powder was milled in planetary ball mill. Here particles of metal powder are repeatedly flattened, fractured and rewelded. Kinetic energy of alloying with phase transformation induced during milling depends upon energy transferred by balls to the powder ^[14]. Energy transfer is governed by many parameters such as type of mill, milling speed, type, size and size distribution of the balls, ball to powder weight ratio, extent of filling of the vials, dry or wet milling, temperature of milling, atmosphere of mill and duration of milling ^[15]. Claudio de Castro et al. ^[16] has reported the effect of energy input by milling iron powder with the use of a SPEX (shaker) milling machine and a Pulverisette 5 (Planetary Ball Milling), among other lower energy mills. They determined that SPEX shaker mills provide the larger input and therefore leads to a fast decrease of grain size to less than 20 nm. The steady state grain size was achieved after 4 h of milling. The pulverisette mill provides a smaller energy impact during collision. After 32h of milling the grain size achieved was 40 nm at 90 r.p.m, 31 nm at 180 r.p.m and 20 nm at 360 r.p.m. Milling times generally decrease with increasing charge ratio C_R as well as larger diameter balls correspond to shorter milling time, which can be understood qualitatively considering that larger balls result higher milling intensities ^[17]. Milling temperature has been observed to affect the rate at which the nanocrystalline structure develops ^[18]. Fracture in particles is more likely when the milling is done under Argon atmosphere, whereas welding between particles is predominant when milling is done in air ^[16].

One way of following the mechanical alloying process is by considering it as a sequence of time periods characterized by important events or powder properties. Process can be broken down into five time intervals: Initial period, Period of welding predominance, Period of equiaxed particle formation, Start of random welding orientation, steady state processing ^[19].

SECTION II: Thin Film Technology for Deposition of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Absorber Layer

2.11 Introduction ^[20, 21]

The deposition of thin films has made a tremendous impact on the level of technology we utilize in our daily life. Thin film coatings provide enhanced optical performance on items ranging from camera lenses to sunglasses. Architectural glass is often coated to reduce the heat load in large office buildings, and provide significant cost saving by reducing air conditioning requirements. Although the study of thin – film phenomenon dates back well over a century, it is only over the last two decades that they have been used to a significant level in practical applications. A solid material is said to be in thin film form when it is built up, as a thin layer on a solid support called substrate. Thickness of thin film is less than one micron (i.e. 10,000 Angstroms/ 1000 nm).

Early references to the science of thin – film deposition include the research conducted by Michael Faraday in 1857. In his series of experiments, Faraday created thin metallic films by exploding metal wires in a vacuum vessel. Historically, the techniques for thin film deposition have evolved in approximately this order: Thermally induced evaporation (by electrical resistance heating, induced heating & electron beam heating), sputtering (diode, triode, magnetron and ion beam), arc processes and most recently laser ablation. The possibility of depositing thin metal films in a vacuum by joule heating of platinum wires was discovered in 1887 by Nahrwold and a year later adapted by Kundt for the purpose of measuring refractive indices of metal films.

2.12 Methods of Thin – film Deposition ^[21]

- Physical Vapour Deposition (PVD)
- Electro – Chemical Deposition (Galvanic)
- Liquid Phase Epitaxy
- Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD)

-
- Plasma Spray

Physical Vapour Deposition

1. Thermal Vacuum Evaporation
2. Electron Beam Evaporation
3. Ion – Beam Sputtering
4. Magnetron Sputtering
5. Laser Ablation

2.12.1 Thermal Vacuum Evaporation

Thermal vacuum evaporation is most widely used technique for preparation of thin films. A schematic representation of the process is shown in Fig. 2.7. The physical stages of film formation consist of several distinguishable steps as:

1. Sublimation of the material to be deposited to the vapour phase.
2. Transfer of vapours from the evaporant to the substrate.
3. Condensation of vapours upon arrival on the substrate.
4. Rearrangement or modification of their binding on the substrate surface.

The characteristics of the films are influenced by rate of evaporation, pressure during deposition, thickness of the film, angle of evaporation, temperature of the substrate and residual atmosphere. Simplest type of thermal vacuum evaporation is the evaporation by electrical resistance of source material. Vapours are produced in a vacuum environment by heating elemental metal, an alloy or a mixture. Electrical power feed through are used to bring high current and low voltage. The electrical power is passed through a filament upon which the charge is present. This filament is heated upto 1000 - 2000°C based on melting point of evaporant. A materials requirement for efficient thermal evaporation is that the charge has an appreciable vapour pressure at the operating temperature of the filament.

Fig. – 2.7: Schematic Diagram of Electrical Resistance Heated thermal Evaporation

2.12.2 *Electron Beam Evaporation*

A beam of energetic electrons generated from a heated filament supplies the thermal energy to evaporate the charge as shown in Fig. 2.8. In electron beam thermal evaporation systems there is one anode which is positively charged and a cathode biased negatively with respect to anode. Based on the electron beam incident on the substrate there are two types of electron beam evaporators:

1. Self-accelerated electron beam evaporators.
2. Work-accelerated electron beam evaporators.

Electron beam evaporation process is normally performed under UHV [Ultra High Vacuum condition]. The evaporant generally travels in a straight-line path from the source to the substrate. To aid in attaining uniform thickness coatings by this technique, substrates are often mounted on “Carousels” which rotate, or spin individual substrate. Deposition shielding is often placed inside the vacuum vessel to facilitate cleaning.

Fig. – 2.8: Schematic Diagram of Electron Beam Evaporator.

2.12.3 Sputter Deposition of Thin Films

In sputter deposition material is made to go into vapour phase by the physical interaction of particles impacting the source material (i.e. Target). There is a wide variety of sputtering techniques that are currently used to deposit thin films for use in magnetic storage media, optical thin films & micro – circuit.

2.12.3.1 Magnetron Sputter Deposition

Magnets situated beside or underneath the target of a diode sputtering source can be used to constrain the electrons emitted from the cathode to orbit in close proximity of the cathode. The probability that such an orbiting electron will strike a process gas molecule, causing ionization is greatly increased without the need to increase process gas pressure. The strength of the magnetic field and placement of the magnets with respect to the cathode is crucial to the proper operation of a magnetron sputter deposition source.

The DC magnetron sputter deposition source has found wide application in industry. Deposition systems using this source range from desktop units for deposition of thin

films for prototype electronic devices, to 150' long architectural glass coating chambers. This chambers use arrays of magnetron sputter guns to coat 4 x 8 foot sheets of glass with several layers in a single pass. Sputtering of all areas of the gun except the cathode is prevented by the use of a ground plane shield. These shields along with the water cooling lines are electrically insulated from the high voltage applied to the cathode through the use of ceramic insulating spacers. Figure 2.9 shows the schematic of Magnetron sputter gun for thin film deposition.

Fig. – 2.9: Schematic Diagram of Thin Film deposition by Magnetron Sputter Gun

2.12.3.2 Ion – beam Sputtering

Special ion sources are used to generate ions and accelerate these ions towards a sputtering target as shown in the Fig. 2.10. The material sputtered from the target by impact of the energetic ions forms the coating on the substrate. In the Kaufman ion sources, electrons emitted from the heated filament (cathode) are attracted to the anode, but the strong magnetic field prevents this. Gas molecules impacted by the oscillating electrons become ionized and being positively charged is attracted to the negatively biased accelerator grid. By controlling the bias applied to the screen and accelerator grids a certain amount of ion – beam focusing may be accomplished.

For a typical 10 cm diameter Kaufman ion – source the characteristics of the ion – beam are as follows:

Argon ion current: 1 to 2 mA/cm²

Argon ion energy: 500 to 2000 eV

Through control of the operating parameters, the ion – current density and the ion energy of the beam may be independently varied. Ion – beam sources are used in laboratories to produce high purity thin film coatings for research & development.

Fig. – 2.10: Schematic Diagram of Thin Film Deposition by Ion – Beam Sputtering

2.12.4 Laser Ablation

High energy density pulsed laser beams have been used to deposit thin films of a variety of elements, alloys and compounds. In this process a laser source external to the vacuum vessel generates a beam which is focused passed through a view part and impinges on a target within the vacuum vessel. Sufficient energy is generated to blast (ablate) materials from the surface of the target. This ablated material consists of neutral atoms, ions and clusters of atoms and macro particles. Figure 2.11 shows the schematic diagram of Laser ablation process.

The amount of material deposited per laser pulse is very consistent, allowing one to accurately deposit films of a specified thickness. The deposition rate is low compared

to other techniques. The range of commonly used operating parameters is given below:

Laser power:	100 to 500 mJ
Spot size at target:	0.1 to 0.25 cm ²
Power density at target:	400 to 5000 mJ/cm ²
Pulse duration:	5 to 50 ns
Wavelength:	250 to 308 nm
Pulse frequency:	1 to 20 Hz

Fig. – 2.11: Schematic Diagram of Thin Film Deposition by Laser Ablation

Laser ablation as a deposition technique is currently limited to research and development laboratories, due to the low deposition rate. In addition to this, there are safety issues such as use of UV lasers and high cost of the equipment.

2.13 Evolution of thin – film from vapour phase

Polycrystalline thin – films are becoming very popular among research community in lieu of their vast applications in advanced technologies. Thin film technology covers areas such as information storage materials, surface coatings (hard or soft coating, protective coating etc.), optical coatings, active and passive layers in micro – electronic devices and combination of these ^[22]. Thin film evolution is primarily based on impingement of controlled amount of atoms, on a well characterized substrate, at a predetermined set of growth conditions. It is possible to grow thin

films having desired properties and textures if growth conditions are studied at atomic level [23].

The first step in the thin film deposition process is the formation of vapour, as vapour covers larger volume and thus separates atoms, molecules and ionic species. The atoms and molecules in these vapour phase arrives on the substrate surface, among this not all the vapours will be adsorbed on substrate but a small fraction will be re – evaporated. The adsorbed species are not in thermal equilibrium and it will move on substrate surface. This atom will join together by bonding and form a larger cluster. This step is known as nucleation. Mobility of adatoms (adsorbed atoms) on surface is important to produce smooth and uniform films. This is obtained by high substrate temperature and kinetic energy of incident atoms. In extreme cases there is a zero mobility parallel to the surface due to which adatoms stays where it has landed and thus amorphous deposit layer will be formed [23].

Figure 2.12 is a graph indicating how growth rate and substrate temperatures influence structure of thin film grown from vapour phase. The mobility of deposited adatoms partially depends on incident kinetic energy. A high incident kinetic energy may induce surface migration even at low substrate temperature.

Fig. – 2.12: Graph indicating forms of Film Generation based on Deposition rate and Substrate Temperature.

The as deposited atoms join together and form a nuclei called island. The nucleation density and size of nucleus depends on number of parameters such as energy of impinging species, rate of impingement, activation energies of adsorption, desorption, thermal diffusion and temperature, topography and chemical nature of the substrate [20]. There is a cohesive energy between the atoms which prevents it from dissociation. This cohesive energy is initially negative as the edges of the islands

have fewer neighbour, thus unsaturated bonds. To nucleate an island enough atoms have to meet to make boundary free energy positive. In nucleation theory, the "critical island size" ' i ' is defined as the size at which for the first time the island becomes more stable with the addition of just one more atom ^[23].

A nucleus can grow both parallel to the substrate by surface diffusion of adsorbed species as well as perpendicular to it by direct impingement of the incident species. Initially rate of growth in lateral direction is much more than in perpendicular direction. Coalescence is a process of grain growth by grain boundary migration, in which adjacent discrete crystals approach and touch each other. An intergranular area developed will influence the growth and reorganization of the coalescing crystal structure. Coalescence is strongly modified by the presence of impurities on the surface of growing discrete individual crystals. The contamination of contacting surface can hinder the complete coalescence as well as filling up of necks. Impurity phase can also develop pores in the neck areas and stop the grain boundary migration. At the end of coalescence continuous film is formed by movement of grain boundaries.

Driving force for grain boundary migrations are grain boundary energy and free surface energy of their neighbouring crystals. Initial stage of grain growth leads to bimodal grain size distribution. At high purity condition and high substrate temperature T , this bimodal grain size distribution can be transformed to monomodal distribution. Under moderate level of contamination grain growth will be stabilized at bimodal grain size distribution. At high contamination level no grain growth occurs and grain boundaries are contaminated and stabilized as the film becomes continuous.

2.13.1 Grain Structure Development

Grain structure development is based on theories that describe the manner in which structure of polycrystalline film depends on substrate temperature. As shown in Fig. 2.13, there are four distinct types of grain morphologies can be produced with increasing temperature: at a very low temperature zone I, no bulk diffusion exists and the surface diffusion is limited. Grain structure in this zone is in fibrous bundles as obtained in primary crystals developed in first stage of deposition.

Fig. – 2.13: Structure Zone Model based on Substrate Temperature

The size of this equiaxed grains increases with increase in substrate and source temperature. This change is attributed to high surface mobility of impinging atoms. As mentioned by K.L. Chopra ^[20] in his book, "Grain growth obtained during post deposition annealing is significantly reduced than that obtained by depositing the film at annealing temperatures. Reason for this is the involvement of high activation energy process of thermal diffusion of the condensate atoms in the former case, as compared to the process of condensation of mobile species in the latter".

The Structure Zone Model at low, medium, and high impurity level is shown in Fig. 2.14. In slightly higher temperature range, Zone T surface mobility increases resulting into competitive growth of primary crystals of random orientation. This competitive growth will improve morphology and orientation across the film thickness. In zone II the grains start to enlarge through the entire thickness of the film, a process mentioned as 'granular epitaxy' by Grovneor et al. ^[11], while diameter of grains remain small. Zone III is mainly composed of single crystalline columns. Grain size increases with increasing temperature. The films are homogenous in the whole thickness. The two sharp changes in grain morphologies are observed at Zone I/ Zone T and other is at Zone T/ Zone II. In area one Zone I to Zone T the grain formation takes place at low substrate temperature so grain size distribution is bimodal i.e. few grains with a very

large size compared to their neighbours. At high substrate temperature between Zone T to Zone II grain boundaries have reasonably high mobilities. Thus all grains will be having same size distribution across film thickness.

Fig. – 2.14: Structure Zone Model at a) Low, b) Medium, c) High impurity Level

The position of zone boundaries in actual deposition conditions depends on levels of impurities apart from substrate temperature. Two major possibilities of contamination are by adsorption of gaseous contaminant species on surface or by impurities due to alloying element present in an evaporant. These contaminations can hinder grain boundary mobility and reduce the development of grain structure in Zone II and Zone III. In contaminated or alloyed films the fibrous Zone I structure may prevail even at high substrate temperature.

SECTION III: Vacuum Techniques for Thin Film Deposition

2.14 Fundamentals of Vacuum Technology

2.14.1 Definition

Design and construction of vacuum system is one of the most useful skill an experimentalist in condensed matter, atomic or optical physics can have ^[24]. According to the definition of the American Vacuum Society (1958) the term "Vacuum" refers to a given space filled with gas at pressures below atmospheric, i.e. having a density of molecules less than about 2.5×10^{19} molecules/cm³ ^[25].

2.14.2 Vacuum Terminology ^[25]

Molecular Density

Molecular density is the average number of molecules per unit volume.

Mean free Path

Mean free path is the average distance that a molecule travels in gas between two successive collisions with other molecules of that gas.

Time to form a monolayer

Time to form a monolayer is the time required for a freely cleaved surface to be covered by a layer of the gas of one molecule thickness. This time is given by the ratio between monolayer (about 8×10^{14} molecule/cm²) and the molecular incidence rate.

Low (and medium) vacuum

The number of molecules of the gas phase is large compared to that covering the surface. Thus in this range the pumping is directed towards rarefying the existing gas phase. The range extends from atmospheric pressure to about 10^{-2} Torr.

High Vacuum

The gas molecules in the system are located principally on surfaces, and the mean free path equals or is greater than the pertinent dimensions of the enclosure. Therefore the pumping consists in evacuating or capturing the molecules leaving the surface and individually reaching the pump.

Ultra - High Vacuum

Ultra - high vacuum is the time to form a monolayer is equal or longer than the usual time for laboratory measurements, thus “clean” surfaces can be prepared and their properties can be determined before the adsorbed gas layer is formed.

Composition of the gas

While the total pressure in a vacuum chamber decreases the composition of the gas phase changes as well. In the low vacuum range the composition of the gas mainly resembles that of the atmosphere. In the high vacuum range the composition changes continuously, toward one which contains 70 – 90% water vapour.

In the ultra – high vacuum range hydrogen is the dominant component coming mostly from the bulk of the materials.

2.14.3 Vacuum Measurement ^[26]

The units for expressing the amount of pressure remaining in a vacuum system are based on the force of atmospheric air under standard conditions. The force amounts to 1.03 kg/cm². In vacuum work the most common units are the torr and millitorr (mtorr). One torr is the equivalent of one millimeter (mm) or 1/760 of atmospheric pressure.

$$1 \text{ mbar} = 0.75 \text{ torr} = 7.5 \times 10^2 \mu$$

2.14.4 Flow Types ^[26]

As a vacuum system is pumped down, the gas goes through four types of flow, they are:

1. Turbulent: Irregular condition of flow with many eddies.
2. Viscous: Regular condition of flow with no eddies.

3. Knudsen: The mean free path is smaller than the pipe diameter.
4. Molecular: The mean free path is larger than the tube diameter and the molecules are independent of each other.

Ranges of each type of flow vary considerably. The major determining factors are the pumping speed and the diameter of the piping through which the gas is passing.

2.15 Equipments for Vacuum Generation

2.15.1 Positive Displacement Oil – Sealed Pump ^[25, 26]

The mechanical or rotary oil – sealed pumps are also called roughing, backing, fore or holding pumps depending on their use. They can connect directly to a vacuum system and discharge into the atmosphere or be used as a backing pump for another type of pump. Figure 2.15 show the cross-section of Oil sealed rotary pump. The sliding vane pump has a cylindrical rotor located off center in a cylindrical housing. The rotor pump carrier two vanes 180° apart, spring loaded so as to ride on the stationary housing.

- | | | |
|------------------|-----------|------------|
| 1.) Outlet Valve | 3.) Rotor | 5.) Vanes |
| 2.) Seal | 4.) Inlet | 6.) Stator |

Fig. – 2.15: Schematic diagram of Oil Sealed Rotary Pump

The inlet part and exhaust valves are separated by a contact area where the housing is machined to the same radius as the rotor. A film of oil is used on all moving parts to lubricate and seal the pump. At pressures near the ultimate, however a number of factors should be considered. The oil must provide proper lubrication and not contribute to the pressure in the evacuated container. However gas can become

entrained in the oil and be transformed from the exhaust part to the inlet by the natural flow of the oil in the pump. It is clear then that the problem of sealing clearances with oil, entrainment of air and ejection of oil slug are important in determining the ultimate pressure of a pump.

Generally speaking, the ultimate pressure of oil sealed rotary pumps is limited by the vapour pressure of the oil & leakage of air past the seal between the exhaust and inlet parts. All oil – sealed pumps have an oil reservoir because the oil film is used as a seal on the valve seat. The capacity of the reservoir is determined by the pump speed and the service requirements. In the early stages of evacuation the ejected air will contain a large amount of oil mist. For that reason the ejected air is exhausted through a mist eliminator^[26].

2.15.2 Diffusion Pump^[26, 27]

The diffusion pump is known as a “fluid entrainment pump” and works in a completely different manner as compared to mechanical pump. The diffusion pump uses the vapour of a boiling fluid to capture air molecules. The fluid is then moved to another location and cooled. The cooling forces the air molecules to be released. The combination of gravity and the downward direction of the vapour move air molecules toward the bottom of the pump.

As shown in the Fig. 2.16, at the bottom there is a heater lying below the oil. When the oil becomes hot enough to vapourise, the oil vapour rises up the center of the pump and exit the nozzles pointing at a downward angle. These nozzles are in a ring and form a curtain or “skirt” of vapour that extends from the nozzles to the pump wall. Any air molecules that passing through inlet diffuses into oil vapours. When the oil vapour hits the water cooled walls of the pump, the oil gets condensed on the sides of the pump. As the oil flows towards the reservoir it releases the air molecules and again begins new cycles. Gas molecules that rise from previous cycles are again diffused into the vapour jet and forced downwards. By continually forcing the air molecules downward high pressure is generated at bottom of pump compared to top. High pressure air accumulated at the bottom is pumped out by a rotary mechanical pump.

Fig. – 2.16: Schematic diagram of Diffusion Pump

Important considerations for operation of a diffusion pump:

- Quality of oil should be such that it maximizes the performance of system and minimizes the need for maintenance.
- Selection of oil should be as per the range of vacuum to be attained. Very high quality, low vacuum applications such as semiconductor or laboratory work requires 705 oil.
- Sufficient amount of cooling has to be applied.

2.16 Vacuum Measuring Equipments

2.16.1 Pirani Gauge ^[25, 28]

Pirani gauge is named after its inventor Marcello Pirani who invented this gauge in 1906. Since then it is widely used for vacuum measurements. The Pirani gauge as shown in Fig. 2.17 consists of a metal filament with high temperature coefficient of resistance such as platinum and tungsten. Principle of working for pirani gauge is based on thermo conductivity as a function of gas pressure. The usual control circuit used for pirani gauge is Wheatstone bridge, in which one leg of the bridge is the filament of the gauge tube and the other legs have resistance nearly equal to that of the gauge tube. Joule heat in the amount $i^2 R_G$ is produced by a current passing through a wire of resistance R_G . Gas molecules collide with the wire, transferring the heat away from it and unbalancing the bridge relative to the reference state.

Fig.– 2.17: Schematic Diagram of Pirani Vacuum Gauge

The heat loss from the wire can take place by convection, conduction or radiation. When the density of gas is high in a gauge head which indicates higher pressure, heat loss takes place by convection; however this convection is not pressure sensitive. In the pressure range of about 200 Torr to 0.1 mTorr conduction dominates and the heat transfer is pressure sensitive. Decrease in heat of wire will reduce its temperature and resistance and consequently current through the unbalanced bridge indicates change in pressure. This method is known as constant voltage mode and it is used in commercial gauges. The most applicable range of this gauge is 10^{-3} to 10^{-1} torr. Other types of pirani gauges work at constant temperature of the sensing wire and utilize heat input as a measure of pressure.

Conventional pirani gauge has certain drawbacks:

- High temperature of filament ($\sim 100^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 150°C above ambient) can cause problem when gases are thermally reactive.
- Reactive gases can coat the wire element and affect its electrical resistance to pressure variations.
- Heat dissipation from the heated filament to the cool instrument wall.
- Convective flow of gas in the gauge is sensitive to mounting position because gravity affects convective current within the gauge.
- Heat transfer mechanism in the gauge depends on composition of gas being measured, since the heat capacity of gas affects heat transfer.

2.16.2 Cold Cathode Ionization Gauge (Penning Gauge)

Ionization vacuum gauge which operates with cold discharge is known as cold cathode or Penning vacuum gauges shown in Fig. 2.18. This type of gauge was first designed by Frans Michel Penning in 1937. A common feature for all types of cold cathode ionization vacuum gauge is they contain two unheated electrodes, cathode and an anode. Two parallel cathodes are placed, and in the midway between two cathodes an anode is placed. The cathodes are metal plates with a wire loop anode placed parallel between them. Cold discharge is initiated in these two electrodes and maintained by means of a D.C. voltage (of around 2 KV) so that the discharge continues at very low pressure. At the top of cathodes at both the extreme end two permanent magnets are placed to generate a magnetic field of around 500 Oerstseds. Effect of this magnetic field is to increase the path of electrons long enough so that number of collisions with gas molecules becomes sufficiently large to maintain ion current discharge.

- | | |
|---------------------------------|-----------------------|
| 1. Anode, V=2-10kV | 2. Cathode (grounded) |
| 3. Permanent magnet (0.1-0.2 T) | 4. Bleeder resistor |

Fig. – 2.18: Schematic diagram of a Penning Gauge

Magnetic line of force will cross electric lines of force and this will confine the electrons to a spiral path before striking the anode. The positively charged ions and electrons move to the corresponding electrodes and produce pressure dependent discharge current which is displayed on meter. The range of the Penning gauge is about $10^{-2} - 10^{-6}$ Torr. The upper limit ($> 10^{-2}$ m bar) of the Penning gauge is

restricted by the glow discharge. In this situation electron instead of producing ion current produces intense light and a current generated is independent of pressure, hence not suitable for measurement. Lower limit depends on the density of gas and discharge stops when density is very low.

Output of Penning gauge in terms of ion current also depends upon type of gas, since certain gases are easier to ionize than others. Ionization vacuum gauges are calibrated with nitrogen as the reference gas. To obtain a true pressure for any gas other than nitrogen, the read off pressure must be multiplied by the correction factor for the gas concerned.

The location of a high vacuum gauge is important to get correct pressure readings. For most accurate results it is advisable to position high vacuum gauge at the vacuum chamber ^[29]. The gauge shows a pumping effect due to cathode sputtering and gas gettering, resulting in an initially lower pressure inside the gauge than in the vacuum chamber ^[30]. Sputtered cathode material forms a gettering surface film on the walls of the gauge tube. Cathode material can be affected by formation of thick insulating oxide layer which could hamper the electron emission. Cathode material should be cleaned periodically.

Advantages of penning gauge far outwit its disadvantages. The main advantage of using a Penning gauge are low cost in comparison to all high vacuum measuring instruments, insensitive to sudden entry of air or vibration and easy to operate.

CHAPTER 3

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

3 Experimental Work

3.1 *Synthesis of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Powder Compound*

3.1.1 *High-energy Milling Process for Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ Nanocrystalline Powder Compound*

Pure metal powders of Cu, In, Ga and Se are taken in stoichiometric quantities. The ratio of the powders were maintained as Cu₁In_xGa_(1-x)Se₂ where x = 0.7. Before starting high-energy milling process powder of pure metals are blended to form a fine mixture.

Figure 3.1 and 3.2 show pictorial view of Insmart MBM 07 Planetary Ball Mill used in the experiment for high-energy milling. The jars for high-energy milling are lined with tungsten carbide material to avoid any contamination from stainless steel to the powder compound. The grinding jars are fitted on a frame placed eccentrically on the sun wheel of planetary ball mill. The grinding media used is WC balls of two different sizes of Φ6 mm and Φ10 mm. Balls used for milling process were thoroughly cleaned in an Ultrasonic cleaner for 10 min. This cleaning is necessary to remove any particles on the ball surface from previous operations. This mixture is filled in a stainless steel jars with appropriate number of balls as calculated from C_R. Ball to powder charge ratio (C_R) was taken as 15:1. Argon gas is purged inside the jars before starting milling to avoid any oxidation during high-energy milling.

Machine is switched on once the milling parameters such as Cycle Time, Speed and Direction of Rotation (CW or CCW) are set. As the milling starts the direction of movement of the sun wheel is opposite to that of the grinding jars in the ratio 1: -2, i.e. for one revolution of sun wheel the grinding jar has two revolutions in opposite direction. The grinding balls in the grinding jars are subjected to superimposed rotational movements, which causes the so – called Coriolis forces ^[31]. The difference in speeds between the balls and grinding jars produces an interaction between frictional and impact forces, which releases high dynamic energies. Grinding was performed at a speed of 400 rpm for a period of 2.5 h.

Fig. – 3.1: Insmart MBM 07 Planetary Ball Mill [Side View]

Fig. – 3.2: Insmart MBM 07 Planetary Ball Mill [Front View]

The Specifications of Insmart MBM 07 Planetary Ball Mill is given in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Specifications of Planetary Ball Milling Machine for CIGS

1.	Application	For fine and ultra fine grinding of soft medium and hard materials.
2.	Feed Size	Up to 10 mm
3.	Output Particle Size	1 μ or smaller (depending on characterization of material, number & size of balls, time & speed selection).
4.	Speed	Sun disc speed 40 to 400 r.p.m.
5.	Direction Rotation	Programmable: Forward/Reverse/Alternate with LED indication.
6.	Time	Run time (1 – 999 min/sec) + Off time (1 – 999 min/sec) = 1 cycle, No. of cycles (1 – 999 min/sec); Total time = (Run time + Off time) * No. of cycles.
7.	Number of bowls	2 (Twin)
8.	Material of Bowl	Tungsten Carbide 94.0 % WC, 6.0%Co, Hardness HV = 1300 Kg/mm, Density (approx.) = 14.4 gm/cc.
9.	Power supply	Single phase 230 V A.C., 50/60 Hz, 10 Amp, 2 Pole MCB with earthing.
10.	Motor and Drive	1.5 Kw (2 HP) Microprocessor based variable frequency drive.
11.	Weight & Dimensions	Machine = 300 Kg L x B x H = 860 x 560 x 730 mm.

During high-energy milling samples were collected after 1h, 1.5h, 2h and 2.5h of ball milling for crystallite size measurement by X –Ray diffraction. Characterization of nanocrystalline powder was done by X –Ray diffraction (XRD) analysis using Cu – K α radiation [Brucker AXS, D8 advance diffractometer, λ = 1.541 Å] at 40 KV and 40 mA. Measurements were made for 2 θ values over 10° - 80° with an increment angle of 0.05°.

3.2 Physical Vapour Deposition of Cu(In, Ga)Se_2 Thin Film

3.2.1 Vacuum Coating Unit ^[32]

In our experiment we have deposited thin film of nanocrystalline Cu(In,Ga)Se_2 milled powder with the help of vacuum coating unit from HINDHIVAC model 15F6 as shown in Fig. 3.3. Vacuum coating unit consists of mild steel cabinet, hydraulically operated cylindrical work chamber and a control panel. Mild steel cabinet houses a high speed vacuum pumping system, electrical components necessary for coating and standard base plate.

Fig. – 3.3: HindHIVAC 15F6 Vacuum Coating Unit

3.2.2 Vacuum Chamber ^[32]

The vacuum chamber is rolled from a polished stainless steel sheet, with two circular glass window for visual inspection of coating process. The chamber is rested on a base plate above mild steel cabinet. It can be raised vertically from base plate by hydraulic pressure applied to attached piston. Chamber can be lowered by switching to hoist down, which will open electromagnetic valve. This will drain hydraulic oil into the oil reservoir.

Bottom edge of the vacuum chamber is protected by 'L' type neoprene gasket which also acts as a vacuum tight seal with the base plate. After raising vacuum chamber to certain height it can be swung toward the sides to provide easy loading and unloading operations. Outer walls of chamber are attached with small diameter tubes carrying cooling water to prevent overheating of chamber. At the top of chamber is attached water cooled crystal holder and multipin electrical feed through for thickness measurements. At the bottom of vacuum chamber two valves are fitted from which one is the vent valve for air admittance at the end of coating cycle, and other is fine control needle valve for controlled flow of air into the chamber.

3.2.3 Vacuum Valves ^[32]

High vacuum valve:

- High vacuum valve used in the unit has 6" diameter of diaphragm butterfly valve (asv - 6).
- Its body consists of a ring whose inner surface makes a seal against an 'O' ring on the valve plate.

Air admittance valve:

1. A quarter inch air admittance valve is fitted to the chamber in order to allow the atmospheric air to enter and to load and unload the substrate after the deposition.
2. A needle valve is provided to admit a controlled flow of gas or air into the chamber.

3.2.4 Vacuum System ^[33]

Fig. – 3.4(a): The diagram represents the working of vacuum coating unit and displays various functions to generate high vacuum. System contains three main pumping device namely rotating mechanical pump, diffusion pump and cold trap. These three devices are supported by various components such as valves and baffles which control the action of these pumps.

Fig. – 3.4(b): When the vacuum chamber is to be hoisted up the vent valve is kept open and air is allowed to enter the chamber. This operation is performed to carry out the loading and unloading of substrate in the system.

Fig. – 3.4(c): Roughing operation is the process of taking vacuum chamber at lower pressure ($\sim 10^{-3}$ torr). Operation is performed by mechanical rotary pumps which sweep the air out of roughing lines. Once the desired pressure is reached in vacuum chamber, rotary pumps are used for backing the diffusion pump. Working of diffusion pump is such that it can only exhaust air at below atmospheric pressure.

Fig. – 3.4(d): System shows the diffusion pump operating with high speed jets oil vapours colliding with gas molecules and compress them in direction of mechanical pump. A diffusion pump has a capacity to reduce the system pressure upto 10^{-7} torr. System also shows the water cooled baffle valves located between diffusion pump and cold trap. Baffle valves prevents the oil vapours to escape towards high – vacuum area of the system. Most back - streamed diffusion pump oil molecules gets condensed on internal water – cooled baffle disc and return to diffusion pump as liquid oil. Device shown between baffle valve and evaporation chamber is known as cold trap. Cold trap prevents the oil vapours from diffusing into vacuum chamber and it condenses any vapour in air existing in the system.

Fig. – 3.4: Schematic Diagram Representing Vacuum Systems at Various Stages of Deposition (a) System overview (b) Vent valve open (c) Roughing operation (d) High vacuum generation

3.2.5 Deposition process of $Cu(In, Ga)Se_2$ thin films

■ 3.2.5.1 Substrate Cleaning

A thoroughly cleaned glass beaker is taken and filled with detergent mixed water. Detergent used was Alconox powder precision cleaner which is specially used for glass equipments. The glass substrates were carefully put into this beaker which is then agitated in ultrasonic machine for 15 min. This procedure will remove any contaminants like lint, fingerprints, oil and airborne particulate matter from the surface.

After 15 min. in ultrasonic machine slides were rinsed with distilled water to remove all detergent from the surface. These slides were placed in a clean beaker filled with distilled water in an ultrasonic machine. Finally slides were soaked in boiling acetone vapours such that acetone vapours pass through the substrate surface. This procedure will produce substrate with excellent smooth surface without any harmful contaminants or stains.

■ 3.2.5.2 $Cu(In, Ga)Se_2$ Thin film Deposition

Thin films of CIGS pulverized compound was deposited by using flash evaporation method. Figure 3.5 show the schematic diagram of flash evaporation set-up. The specifications of vacuum coating unit is given in Table 3.2. Flash evaporation of pulverized compound was done under same conditions. Powder is feed through a vibration feeder at a steady rate on a vapour source, which evaporates to form thin film. In this method thermal evaporation of material takes place from vapour source by means of resistive heating.

Fig. – 3.5: Flash Evaporation System for Physical Vapour Deposition

Table 3.2: Specification of Vacuum Coating Unit for Thin film Deposition

Sr. No.	Parameter	Model/Specification
1.	Backing Pump: a.) Oil Sealed Rotary Pump b.) Free Air Displacement (FAD) c.) Motor Rating d.) Oil charge	HindHIVAC, ED – 18 300 lit/min 0.75 H.P., 220 V 2 liters
2.	Motor for Rotary Pump: a.) Make b.) Speed c.) Output	American Universal 1440 r.p.m. 0.55 Kw.
3.	Diffusion Pump: a.) Make b.) Pumping Speed c.) Cooling water supply d.) Volts e.) Oil Charge f.) Heater power	Hind HIVAC, OD 150F 1000 lit/s 20 lit/s 230 V 200 c.c. 4.3 Kw.
4.	Ultimate vacuum (m.bar)	$>1 \times 10^{-6}$ torr
5.	Base plate diameter	15"
6.	LT Evaporation	3set x 200 Amps.
7.	Main supply 50 Hz.	220 V

The process begins with supply of 220V, 15 Amp current to the system. Once system is ON rotary pump is started and backing valve is opened, pressure is measured from pirani gauge indicator. As the pressure reaches 10^{-2} torr backing valve is closed and roughing valve is opened. Pressure drop occurs and system is allowed to reach pressure of $\sim 10^{-3}$ torr. Meanwhile cooling pump is started and system is allowed to cool until a temperature of 20°C. Diffusion pump is started and allowed to run for 20 min until the oil in diffusion pump is vapourised. At pressure of 10^{-3} torr roughing valve is closed and at the same time backing valve and baffle valve are opened.

Substrate heating is carried out up to a temperature of 523°K by increasing voltage through variac. Once the substrate temperature reaches 523°K deposition process is initiated. Deposition starts by LT (Low Tension) supply to evaporation source. Supply voltage through input transformer is set as 230V; this voltage is supplied by parallel connections in the secondary side of the transformer. Substrate is held against the heater surface with stainless steel clamps inside the evaporation chamber. Heating element used is Nichrome and the maximum attainable temperature was set at 523°K. Substrates are uniformly heated at a rate of 3°C/min using this arrangement. Temperature of the substrate is measured by chromel – alumel thermocouple.

In flash evaporation DC voltage applied across the vibration feeder makes it vibrate. These vibrations are transmitted to the hopper through aluminum plate. The powder then falls grain by grain from vibrating hopper onto the 26 mm x 12 mm x 5 mm Molybdenum boat placed below, which is preheated to required temperature. Vapours starts travelling towards 7.5 cm x 2.5 cm sized glass substrate kept at a distance of about 12 cm. The deposition rate can be controlled by controlling DC voltage applied to the vibration feeder. Using the flash evaporation method thin films of different thicknesses i.e. 1517 Å, 2025 Å and 2517 Å are deposited on glass substrate.

Scanning Electron Microscopy image of the film was taken by JEOL JSM 5610 LV scanning electron microscope. Optical characterization was done by UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer. Method for optical characterization is given in section 3.3 and experimental set up is shown in Fig. 3.6. Electrical resistivity was measured by Van der Pauw technique and this method is described in section 3.4.

3.3 Optical characterization of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ thin films

Transmission and reflection measurements of the samples are used to determine the band gap of semiconductor. The band-gap of the sample is determined by observing the wavelength at which the sample begins to absorb the transmitted light. In order to measure the absorption accurately, we must account for the entire light incident, reflected, transmitted, or scattered by the sample.

Fig. 3.6: Experimental setup for optical characterization

From the above setup we can transmission and reflection of the thin films and from that the absorption coefficient (α) was calculated using the following equation;

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{d} \ln \frac{T}{(1-R)^2} \quad (3.1)$$

Here, T = Transmittance.

R = Reflectance.

d = the film's thickness.

The absorption coefficient, α , for a direct transition is related to the band gap of a semiconductor and is given by Following relation;

$$\alpha hv \propto (hv - E_g)^{1/2}. \quad (3.2)$$

Here, hv = photon energy.

E_g = energy gap.

Using the above equation, the plot of $(\alpha hv)^2$ versus hv gives the band gap of the material.

3.4 Electrical Resistivity Measurement by Van der Pauw Method

A schematic of a rectangular Van der Pauw configuration is shown in Fig. 3.7. With the help of above configuration we calculate the resistance between the four vertices. (Resistance between diagonal points and the edge points).

Fig. 3.7: Schematic of a Van der Pauw configuration

The bulk electrical resistivity ρ can be calculated using:

$$\rho = (R_s \times t). \quad (3.3)$$

Where, t is the thickness of the film.

R_s is resistance between two probes.

CHAPTER 4

RESULT AND
DISCUSSION

4 Result and Discussion

4.1 *X – Ray Powder Diffraction Studies of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Powder Compound*^[34]

X – Ray diffraction pattern of milled powder samples are shown in Fig. 4.1- 4.4. Main peaks appear on (112), (220)/ (204), (312)/ (116), (400) and (332) planes indicating chalcopyrite structure of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) compound. Peaks appear to be sharp indicating crystalline phase of compound. In between CIGS peaks intermediate phases of α , β and γ – In₂Se₃ and ternary phase of CuInSe₂ are observed. After high-energy milling, the X-ray diffraction pattern show broadening of peak takes place due to decrease in crystallite size and lattice strain.

Similar experiment was conducted by B. Vidhya et al.^[35], where dry milling of Cu, In, Ga and Se precursors by planetary ball mill was carried out to prepare CuIn_{0.75}Ga_{0.25}Se₂ powder at milling times of 45 min, 1.5, 3, 4.5 and 6 h. X – Ray powder diffraction confirms a CuIn_{0.75}Ga_{0.25}Se₂ phase at 45 minutes of milling time. Apart from well distinguished CIGS peak, minor peak indicating a binary phase of In₂Se₃ compound was observed at $2\theta = 42.54^\circ$. This result is consistent with the result obtained in present experiment. Compounds with binary and ternary phases like α , β & γ – In₂Se₃ at $2\theta = 18.2^\circ$, 30.8° and 39.9° respectively and CuInSe₂ at $2\theta = 47.6^\circ$ were observed for 1.5 h of milling. Presence of Cu, In and Se phases indicate that during first 1.5 hour of milling Ga is not penetrated completely inside the reaction mixture.

Sajid N. Malik et al.^[36] had reported that during synthesis of Cu(In_xGa_(1-x))Se₂ compounds, formation of gallium containing phases would require relatively longer reaction time and/or higher temperatures than those employed for deposition of indium containing phases. Thus longer reaction time and higher temperature can yield stoichiometric combination of CIGS material consistent with molar ratios of indium and gallium precursors used in the reactions.

Sejin Ahn et al. ^[37] has synthesized CIGS nanoparticles by colloidal process. CIGS particles of 15 – 80 nm size range were obtained by reacting CuI, InI₃ and GaI₃ in pyridine with Na₂Se in methanol at 0°C in presence of nitrogen with mechanical stirring. From X – Ray powder diffraction results three main peaks appear at 27.1°, 45.8° and 52.5° respectively well corresponded to (112), (220)/(204) and (312)/(116) planes of chalcopyrite structure.

Similarly Matthew G. Panthani et al. ^[38] has reported the synthesis of Cu(In_xGa_(1-x))Se₂ nanocrystals ranging from ~5 to ~25nm in diameter by arrested precipitation in solution. X – Ray powder diffraction was carried out of CIGS nanocrystals synthesized with Ga/In ratios varying from 0 to 1. All the XRD patterns reveals chalcopyrite (tetragonal) crystal structure and exhibit the expected amount of peak broadening due to their nanoscale crystal domain size. Sejin Ahn et al. ^[37] has stated that broadening and low intensity of the peaks is presumably due to the small size and not well developed crystalline structure of the particles.

In the experiment carried out by Sajid N. Malik et al. ^[36] where he had synthesized nanoparticles by thermolysis of precursors at desired temperatures. Growth temperatures and reaction duration possess a significant effect on size and morphologies of the particles. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern confirms tetragonal chalcopyrite crystallographic phase of CIGS materials. In all cases, a preferential orientation along (112) plane was observed, while other prominent peak originate from (204)/ (220) and (312) plane of the lattice. Relatively broad peaks were obtained which are indicative of crystallite size in nano size domain.

X – Ray powder diffraction obtained in present experiment when compared to standard JCPDS card [142d (122)] shows a slight shift of the peaks towards higher 2θ angles. This shift could be due to lattice distortion caused due to milling. B. Vidhya et al. ^[35] has observed that XRD reflections are slightly left shifted (to lower values of 2θ) with increase in milling time. This is result of internal stresses induced by milling. These internal stresses modify the lattice parameters and consequently produce an angular shift of XRD peak. This shift is clearly visible for 3 h of milling and increase continuously at higher milling duration.

Fig - 4.1: XRD Pattern of CIGS powder compound after 1 h of milling.

Fig - 4.2: XRD Pattern of CIGS powder compound after 1.5 h of milling.

Fig - 4.3 : XRD Pattern of CIGS powder compound after 2 h of milling.

Fig - 4.4: XRD Pattern of CIGS powder compound after 2.5 h of milling.

This is in accordance to statement made by Sherif El – Eskandarany^[39],” The rate of amorphization depends on kinetic energy of the ball mill charge and depends on number of opportunities for the powder particles to be reacted and interdiffused.

In the present experiment XRD results when compared for different milling times reveals minor shift of peaks towards higher 2θ angles, especially for 2.5 h of milling. This shift is possibly due to integration of gallium atom in place of indium and thus changes in lattice parameters. In the experiment done by Layla Al Juhaiman et al.^[40] for the synthesis of $\text{Cu}(\text{In}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x})\text{Se}_2$ by green synthesis route with variable gallium content. Three diffraction peaks corresponding to (112), (220) and (116) planes were observed, confirming the tetragonal chalcopyrite structure. A small but gradual peak shift was clearly observed towards higher angles at (112) peaks for $2\theta = 28^\circ$, as the gallium content is increased. This can be proved from sharp difference of about 0.6° in the peak positions of CuInSe_2 and $\text{CuIn}_{0.5}\text{Ga}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ samples. Sajid N. Malik et al.^[56] and Matthew G. Panthani et al.^[38] has reported such angular shifts in their experiments where gallium content causes the gradual shifting of peaks to higher 2θ angles. When relative smaller gallium atoms substitute indium atoms in the lattice, results in gradual change in lattice parameters (d – spacing).

Table 4.1: Comparison of X – Ray Powder diffraction Results Between Experimental and Standard JCPDS Data

Experimental Diffraction Angle [2 θ in degrees]
27.05
45
53.2

1 h of milling.

Experimental Diffraction Angle [2 θ in degrees]
27.05
44.85
53.3

1.5 h of milling.

Experimental Diffraction Angle [2 θ in degrees]
27.05
45
53.3

2h of milling.

Experimental Diffraction Angle [2 θ in degrees]
27.1
45
53.4

2.5h of milling.

Standard Diffraction Angles [2 θ in degrees] JCPDS card [I42d(122)]
26.898
44.647
52.946

4.2 Determination of Interplanar Spacing (d) and Crystallite Size (D)

Sample – I: After 1h of milling

Calculation of d – Spacing

Applying Bragg's Law i.e. $2d\sin\theta = n\lambda$ to calculate d – spacing.

Taking $n = 1$ and $\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$,

1.) $2\theta = 27.05^\circ$

$\therefore \theta = 13.525^\circ$

$$d = \frac{0.1541}{2 \times \sin 13.525^\circ}$$

$\therefore d = 0.3295 \text{ nm.} \quad (1)$

2.) $2\theta = 45^\circ$

$\therefore \theta = 22.5^\circ$

$$d = \frac{0.1541}{2 \times \sin 22.5^\circ}$$

$\therefore d = 0.2013 \text{ nm.} \quad (2)$

3.) $2\theta = 53.2^\circ$

$\therefore \theta = 26.6^\circ$

$$d = \frac{0.1541}{2 \times \sin 26.6^\circ}$$

$\therefore d = 0.1721 \text{ nm.} \quad (3)$

4.2.1 Analysis of Crystallite Size and Lattice Parameters

Crystallite size is calculated using Scherrer's formula as shown in eqn. 1 and its values are listed in table – 4.2. Fig 4.5 shows the graph of crystallite size with respect to milling time. Crystallite sizes are calculated from FWHM (β) at corresponding angle (2θ) for all milling times. Graph shows decrease in crystallite size with milling time.

$$D = 0.9\lambda / \beta \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{d^2} = \left[(h^2 + k^2)/a^2 + \frac{l^2}{c^2} \right] \quad (2)$$

Crystallite Size Calculation

Crystallite size of powder samples can be calculated by using Scherrer's formula.

$$D = \frac{0.9\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta}$$

Where, β = Fixed Width at Half Maximum (FWHM).

θ = Diffraction angle.

λ = Wavelength of X – Rays.

D = Particle Size.

1.) $2\theta = 27.05^\circ$ and $\beta = 0.01047$ radians

$$D = \frac{0.9 \times 0.1541}{0.01047 \times \cos 13.525^\circ}$$

$$\therefore D = 13.62 \text{ nm.} \quad (4)$$

2.) $2\theta = 45^\circ$ and $\beta = 0.0166$ radians

$$D = \frac{0.9 \times 0.1541}{0.0166 \times \cos 22.5^\circ}$$

$$\therefore D = 9.05 \text{ nm.} \quad (5)$$

3.) $2\theta = 53.2^\circ$ and $\beta = 0.0175$ radians

$$D = \frac{0.9 \times 0.1541}{0.0175 \times \cos 26.6^\circ}$$

$$\therefore D = 8.86 \text{ nm.} \quad (6)$$

Similarly, values of d – spacing and crystallite sizes have been calculated for 1.5h, 2h, 2.5h of milling samples and the results are given in Table – 4.2.

Table 4.2: Results obtained from X – Ray diffraction of CIGS powder

Milling Duration in (hrs.)	Angle of Intensity Peak (2θ) in (deg.)	Angle of Intensity peak (θ) in (deg.)	FWHM (β) of Intensity peak in (radians)	Crystallite Size (D) (nm)	d – spacing (nm)
1	27.05	13.525	0.01047	13.62	0.3295
	45	22.5	0.0166	9.043	0.2013
	53.2	26.6	0.0175	8.86	0.1721
1.5	27.05	13.525	0.01134	13.62	0.3295
	44.85	22.43	0.0183	8.19	0.2019
	53.3	26.65	0.0218	8.47	0.1718
2	27.05	13.525	0.01134	12.58	0.3295
	45	22.5	0.02007	7.48	0.2013
	53.3	26.65	0.02007	7.73	0.1718
2.5	27.1	13.55	0.01309	10.9	0.3289
	45	22.5	0.0209	7.17	0.2013
	53.4	26.7	0.0166	9.35	0.1715

Figure 4.5 shows the effect of milling time on the crystallite size of CIGS powder. It was observed that minimum crystallite size was observed after 1h 45min of milling.

Fig. 4.5: Graph showing crystallite size D with respect to milling time

B. Vidhya et al. ^[35] had reported a decrease in grain size from 12.44 to 7.96 nm with the increase in milling time from 45 minute to 6 h. Mechanical alloying time increases the hardness which leads to fracturing of the agglomerated powder into smaller particles ^[39].

Sejin Ahn et al. ^[37] had observed in his experiment that particle size is significantly affected by the reaction time (mechanical stirring time). As the reaction time increases starting from 0s the size of the particles is first decreased showing a minimum at the reaction time of 1 minute (about 15 nm in diameter with very small size distribution). When the reaction time is increased from 1 minute to 5 minute, the particle size increases abruptly from 15 nm to 70 nm. Further increase in reaction

time (20 to 60 minute) induces slight increase in the particle size. Thus, higher the initial nucleation rate the finer the resultant particles.

Lattice parameters 'a' and 'c' are calculated using eqn. 2 and the values obtained are near to the standard JCPDS I – 42d(122) values. Vegard's law states that there is a linear relationship between the lattice parameter 'c' and the composition x of gallium. Value of lattice parameter 'c' decreases linearly with gradual decrease in indium composition in gallium rich phases ^[36]. Above statement is in accord with the 'c' values calculated in current experiment. As shown in table 4.3, as milling time duration increases values of lattice parameter 'c' decreases. This result supports the fact that milling does improve the composition of CIGS compounds by increasing gallium rich phases.

CIGS compound possess tetragonal chalcopyrite structure with Bravais lattice values given as {x, y, z} = {1, 1, 2}. Each group I element (Cu) and group III element (In/Ga) atoms has four bonds to group VI element (Se). In turn each Se atom has two bonds to Cu and two bonds to In/Ga. As the strength of the group I –VI and group III – VI bonds are in general different, the ratio of the lattice constants c/a is not exactly '2' ^[5]. The above statement is in good agreement with the c/a ratios obtained which are nearly '2' as shown in Table 4.3. Quantity 'U' equals to (2 – c/a) is a measure of the tetragonal distortion in chalcopyrite materials.

Table 4.3: Structural and lattice parameters of CIGS Nanoparticles

Milling Time	FWHM (radians)	a(Å)	c(Å)	c/a	U = 2 - c/a
1 h	0.01047	5.698	11.47	2.012	-0.0129
1.5h	0.01134	5.715	11.39	1.993	0.007
2h	0.01134	5.698	11.46	2.011	-0.0112
2.5h	0.01309	5.698	11.40	2.0007	-0.0007

4.3 *Structural, Optical and Electrical Properties of Flash Evaporated Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Thin Films*

4.3.1 *Scanning Electron Microscopy of Thin Film*

SEM micrograph showing the surface morphology of flash evaporated thin film is in Fig. 4.6a – 4.6d. These films are deposited by flash evaporation on glass slide of 7.5 cm x 2.5 cm at a predisposition temperature of 523° K. The film shown in the micrograph is quiet dense with average distance between grains is 0.5 to 1 μm. Grains shown in SEM images are worm shaped with approximately 0.5 μm in length and 0.08 – 0.1μm in width. These worm like grains possess a white shining appearance above the densely packed plate like background material. L. Yandjah et al. ^[41] has observed similar micrograph in his experiment. Compositional analysis indicates this worm like structure to be Cu – rich in comparison of background material.

In the early stages of deposition, adsorption occurs at discrete nucleation sites. As atoms approach the surface, islands are formed which grows in size until they merge with neighbouring islands to form a continuous coating. The probability of migration for adsorbed atom on the surface is relatively less at lower substrate temperature. Deposition at lower substrate temperature leads to formation of small isolated grains with large number of voids. Surface migration increases at higher substrate temperature resulting in enhanced interaction of adsorbed atoms to form large grains ^[42]. This will have a major effect on the size and number of void present in the film. At higher substrate temperatures, grain distribution becomes uniform and dense as shown in fig. 4.6a - 4.6d. The flash evaporated CIGS thin film shown in SEM image has a significant impact of substrate temperature on its grain growth and follows the theory of nucleation and film formation process reported in earlier chapters.

Fig. - 4.6: Scanning Electron Microscopy Image of CIGS Thin Film deposited at 523°K with film thickness 2517 Å. (a) 500x, (b) 1000x, (c) 2000x and (d) 5000x Magnifications.

4.3.2 Optical Properties of Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ Thin Films

The transmission spectra, absorption spectra and band gap spectra of CIGS thin films of 1517 Å, 2025 Å and 2517 Å thicknesses are shown in Fig. 4.7 – 4.15. Transmission plots for film thickness 1517 Å and 2025 Å shows transmission edge seen at the wavelength range of 900 – 1000 nm. Transmission edge for film thickness 2517 Å is not visible on transmission plot, because the wavelength range of spectrometer used is in the range of 900 – 1800 nm. Maximum transmission for film thickness 1517 Å and 2025 Å is approximately 60 – 65%, and for 2517 Å it is 100% in the wavelength range of 1300 – 1400 nm. Absorption coefficient α obtained from absorption spectra is of the order of 10^{-4} cm^{-1} which is desirable for chalcopyrite thin films. Absorption of photons is more for 1517 Å film at higher wavelength range, while photon absorption for 2025 Å and 2517 Å thickness films is higher at lower wavelength range.

Plots of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ of CIGS films are shown in Fig. 4.12 – 4.15. The presence of a single slope in the curves of the plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ for CIGS suggests that all the films are single phase in nature with direct allowed transition^[43]. The energy band gap of the film is determined by drawing a straight line segment along the curves of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ extrapolating to the energy axis. The variation of band gap with respect to film thickness is shown in Fig. 4.16 in section 4.3.4. The energy band gap values of all the thin films were found to be increasing with increase in film thickness.

4.3.3 Electrical Properties of Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ Thin Film

Resistivity of Cu(In_(1-x)Ga_x)Se₂ samples were calculated using Van der Pauw technique. A spherical dot of silver paste was applied as a contact electrode between probe and film surface. Average resistivity ρ calculated for film thickness 2517 Å was $0.69 \Omega - \text{cm}$, and for 2025 Å value increases to $462.85 \Omega - \text{cm}$. Resistivity ρ for film thickness 1517 Å was too large to be calculated with this technique. Thus as the thickness increases resistivity of the film decreases.

Fig. - 4.7: Transmission Spectra of CIGS Thin film deposited at 523 °K with film thickness 1517 Å

Fig. - 4.8: Transmission Spectra of CIGS Thin film deposited at 523 °K with film thickness 2025 Å

Fig. – 4.9: Transmission Spectra of CIGS Thin film deposited at 523 °K with film thickness 2517 Å

Fig. – 4.10: Absorption Spectra of CIGS Thin film deposited at 523 °K with film thickness 1517 Å

Fig. – 4.11: Absorption Spectra of CIGS Thin film deposited at 523 °K with film thickness 2025 Å

Fig. – 4.12: Absorption Spectra of CIGS Thin film deposited at 523 °K with film thickness 2517 Å

Fig. – 4.13: Energy Band Gap Spectra of CIGS Thin film deposited at 523 °K with film thickness 1517 Å

Fig. - 4.14: Energy Band Gap Spectra of CIGS Thin film deposited at 523 °K with film thickness 2025 Å

Fig. - 4.15: Energy Band Gap Spectra of CIGS Thin film deposited at 523 °K with film thickness 2517 Å

4.3.4 Effect of Film Thickness on the Band Gap Energy(eV)

Table 4.4: Band Gap values for corresponding film thickness

Sr. No.	Film Thickness (Å)	Band Gap (eV)
1	1517	0.78
2	2025	0.93
3	2517	1.09

Fig. 4.16: Variation of Band Gap with increase in Film Thickness

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

5 Conclusion

The conclusions derived from the researchwork are as under:

1. High-energy milling of elemental powders of Copper, Indium, Gallium and Selenium appears a suitable process for the production of $\text{Cu}(\text{In,Ga})\text{Se}_2$ (CIGS) having chalcopyrite structure. Gallium incorporation into the compound mixture increases with the increase in milling time.
2. The milled CIGS powder has crystallite size less than 15 nm after one hour of milling. Milling also decreases the size of the powder particles. Small size of powder particles is advantageous for thermal flash evaporation as it increases the evaporation rate and results into complete evaporation. Thus it reduces deposition time and material cost.
3. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) image of as-deposited CIGS thin film deposited by flash evaporation method at a substrate temperature of 523°K shows shining white worm like grains on the surface. Annealing of the thin film at higher temperature can result into interdiffusion of these grains and produce uniform surface.
4. Optical characterization results shows that, as the thickness increases transmission and absorption of photons improves in the CIGS thin films.
5. Band gap spectra of CIGS thin films with three different thicknesses (i.e. 1517 Å, 2025 Å and 2517 Å) show that, band gap energy increases with increase in thickness of film. Band gap energy of film thickness 2517 Å is 1.09 eV which matches with the literature data for CIGS thin films ^[6].
6. Electrical characterization was done by Vander Pauw technique. Results show that resistivity ρ decreases with film thickness. Low value of resistivity is desirable for preparation of absorber layer for thin film solar cells ^[44].

Finally, it can be concluded that $\text{Cu}(\text{In,Ga})\text{Se}_2$ nanocrystalline powder can be synthesized by high-energy milling. The synthesized CIGS powder can be used for thin film preparation by thermal flash evaporation under high vacuum condition for absorber layer of solar cells.

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Appendix – I

Table 3.5 JCPDS card 00-035-1102 (CIGS)

<i>Pattern:</i> 00-035-1102		<i>Radiation</i> = 1.540600 <i>Quality:</i> Indexed				
CuGa_{0.3}In_{0.7}Se₂		2θ	Int.	h	k	l
Copper Gallium Indium Selenide		17.272	7	1	0	1
		26.898	100	1	1	2
		28.037	1	1	0	3
		35.862	2	2	1	1
<i>Lattice:</i> Body-centered tetragonal <i>SG:</i> I-42d (121)		42.423	1	2	1	3
<i>Mol. Weight</i> =322.76		42.423	1	1	0	5
<i>Volume/CD</i> =376.66		44.647	40	2	2	0
<i>a</i> =5.73600	<i>Z</i> =4	44.647	40	2	0	4
<i>c</i> =11.44800		48.213	1	3	0	1
		52.946	25	3	1	2
		52.946	25	1	1	6
		63.300	1	3	2	3
<i>Sample preparation:</i> Samples were melt grown by heating the components with exact stoichiometric ratio in a evacuated sealed silica tube at 1170 K for several hours then slowly cooled to room temperature over 2 days. <i>Data collection flag:</i> Ambient.		63.300	1	3	0	5
		64.982	5	4	0	0
		65.135	3	0	0	8
		67.805	1	4	1	1
		67.805	1	2	1	7
		71.716	5	3	3	2
		71.716	5	3	1	6
		82.352	6	4	2	4
		82.352	6	2	2	8
		85.017	1	5	0	1
		88.592	3	5	1	2
		88.592	3	3	3	6
		93.221	1	5	2	1
		93.221	1	4	1	7
		99.002	4	4	4	0
		99.002	4	4	0	8
<i>Grzein-Plenkovic, B. Et al., J. Appl. Crystallog., volume 13, page 311 (1980)</i>		105.222	3	5	3	2
		105.362	3	5	1	6
		105.362	3	3	1	10
		116.369	2	6	2	0
		116.369	2	6	0	4
<i>Radiation:</i> CuKα						
<i>Lambda:</i> 1.54178						
<i>SS/FOM:</i> F21=6(0.0410, 83)						
<i>Filter:</i> Ni						
<i>d-sp:</i> Diffractometer						
<i>d-sp:</i> MgO						

Appendix – II

Table 3.4 JCPDS card 03-065-2740 (CuInSe₂)

<i>Pattern:</i> 03-065-2740		<i>Radiation</i> = 1.540600 <i>Quality:</i> Calculated				
		2θ	Int.	h	k	l
CuInSe ₂		17.122	34	1	0	1
		26.666	999	1	1	2
Copper Indium Selenide		27.774	45	1	0	3
		30.890	10	0	0	4
<i>Lattice:</i> Body-centered tetragonal <i>S.G.:</i> I-42d (122)		30.890	10	2	0	0
		34.642	1	2	0	2
<i>a</i> =5.78500 <i>c</i> =11.57300		35.527	55	2	1	1
		42.016	26	1	0	5
<i>Z</i> =4		42.016	26	2	1	3
		44.243	626	2	0	4
		44.243	626	2	2	0
		47.779	20	3	0	1
<i>NIST M&A collection code:</i> NAL2387 3456 <i>Temperature factor:</i> IB=Cu, In, Se <i>Data collection flag:</i> Ambient		49.850	1	3	1	0
		52.414	337	1	1	6
		52.414	337	3	1	2
		53.045	7	2	1	5
		53.045	7	3	0	3
		54.932	3	2	2	4
		57.372	1	2	0	6
		57.984	4	1	0	7
		57.984	4	3	2	1
		59.760	1	3	1	4
		62.660	18	3	0	5
		62.660	18	3	2	3
		64.365	78	0	0	8
		64.365	78	4	0	0
		66.597	1	4	0	2
		67.137	13	2	1	7
H. Hahn, G. Frank, W. Klingler, A.-D. Meyer & G. Storger, <i>Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.</i> , Volume 217, page 153 (1953) Calculated from NIST using POWD-12++		67.137	13	4	1	1
		70.949	108	3	1	6
		70.949	108	3	3	2
		71.488	19	3	2	5
		71.488	19	4	1	3
		73.094	4	4	0	4
		73.094	4	4	2	0
		75.205	1	4	2	2
<i>Radiation:</i> CuKα <i>Lambda:</i> 1.54180 <i>SS/FOM:</i> F30=187(0.0033, 48)		75.718	5	1	0	9
		75.718	5	3	0	7
		79.883	6	4	1	5

Appendix – III

Table 3.1 JCPDS card 00-034-1279 (α -In₂Se₃)

<i>Pattern:</i> 00-034-1279		<i>Radiation</i> = 1.540600 <i>Quality:</i> Indexed						
		2θ	Int.	<i>h</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>l</i>		
α -In ₂ Se ₃		9.205	10	0	0	2		
		18.431	100	0	0	4		
Indium Selenide		25.532	1	1	0	0		
		25.956	1	1	0	1		
<i>Latice:</i> Hexagonal		27.208	12	1	0	2		
<i>S.G.:</i> P63/mmc (194)		27.814	50	0	0	6		
<i>Mol. Weight:</i> 466.52		29.131	5	1	0	3		
<i>Volume(CD):</i> 269.87		31.681	1	1	0	4		
<i>a</i> =4.02500	<i>Z</i> =2	34.743	8	1	0	5		
<i>c</i> =19.23500		<i>D_v</i> =5.741	37.377	7	0	0	8	
<i>Sample preparation:</i> Prepared by direct synthesis from the components in vacuum with exact stoichiometric ratio at 1188K, then slowly cooled to room temperature over two days. <i>Data collection flag:</i> Ambient.		38.101	9	1	0	6		
		41.846	2	1	0	7		
		45.045	16	1	1	0		
		45.814	12	1	0	8		
		47.228	16	0	0	10		
		49.043	6	1	1	4		
		49.991	8	1	0	9		
		53.413	2	2	0	2		
		54.547	1	2	0	3		
		57.441	3	0	0	12		
		58.115	1	2	0	5		
		59.096	1	1	0	11		
		60.415	1	2	0	6		
		63.932	2	1	0	12		
		66.176	1	2	0	8		
		67.307	3	1	1	10		
		68.198	14	0	0	14		
		69.583	1	2	0	9		
		Popovic, S. et al., <i>J. Appl. Crystallogr.</i> , volume 12, page 416 (1979)		71.716	1	2	1	1
				74.133	1	1	0	14
75.798	1			1	1	12		
78.459	1			2	1	6		
79.631	1			0	0			
83.219	2			3	0	0		
83.219	2			3	0	1		
<i>Radiation:</i> CuK α <i>Lambda:</i> 1.54180 <i>SS/FOM:</i> F30=35(0.0200, 43)		85.481	9	1	1	14		
		91.324	1	2	0	14		
		91.324	1	1	0			
		92.205	2	0	0			
		99.940	1	2	2	0		
		109.458	2	1	1			
<i>Filter:</i> Not specified <i>d-sp:</i> Diffractometer								

Appendix – IV

Table 3.2 JCPDS card 00-035-1056 (β -In₂Se₃)

<i>Pattern:</i> 00-035-1056		<i>Radiation</i> = 1.540600 <i>Quality:</i> Not indexed				
β -In ₂ Se ₃		2θ	Int.	h	k	l
Indium Selenide		0.631	16	0	0	3
		18.785	100	0	0	6
		25.879	5	1	0	1
		28.355	12	0	0	9
<i>Lattice:</i> Rhombohedral		30.210	30	0	1	5
<i>S.G.:</i> R-3m (166)		36.282	4	0	1	8
<i>Mol. Weight:</i> 466.52		38.101	6	0	0	12
<i>Volume(CDF):</i> 392.55		41.167	20	1	0	10
<i>a:</i> 4.00000	<i>Z:</i> 3	43.782	7	0	1	11
<i>c:</i> 28.33000		45.306	16	1	1	0
		48.131	25	0	0	15
		49.469	5	1	1	6
<i>Sample preparation:</i> Transformed from α -phase at 473 K.		55.587	4	2	0	5
<i>Temperature of data collection:</i> Pattern taken at 478 K.		58.519	12	1	0	
<i>General comments:</i> Will transform back to α phase at 360-330 K.		58.519	12	0	0	
<i>Data collection flag:</i> Non ambient temperature.		61.662	3	0	1	
		62.965	4	0	2	10
		68.255	3	1	1	15
		74.473	5	1	2	5
		77.177	2	1	1	
		82.783	3	1	2	11
		94.264	2	0	0	
Popovic, S. et al., J. Appl. Crystallogr., volume 12, page 416 (1979)						
<i>Radiation:</i> CuK α						
<i>Lambda:</i> 1.54180						
<i>SS/FOM:</i> F21=6(0.0620, 62)						
<i>Filter:</i> Not specified						
<i>d-sp:</i> Debye-Scherrer						

Appendix – V

Table 3.3 JCPDS card 00-040-1407 (γ - In_2Se_3)

<i>Pattern:</i> 00-040-1407		<i>Radiation</i> = 1.540600 <i>Quality:</i> High				
γ - In_2Se_3		2 θ	Int.	h	k	l
Indium Selenide		15.049	21	1	0	1
		17.004	51	1	0	2
		23.338	9	1	0	4
		24.968	77	1	1	0
<i>Lattice:</i> Hexagonal		35.377	6	1	1	1
<i>S.G.:</i> P61 (169)		27.141	12	1	0	5
<i>Mol. Weight:</i> 466.52		27.587	81	0	0	6
<i>Volume(CD):</i> 852.98		28.586	25	1	1	3
<i>a:</i> 7.12860	<i>Z:</i> 6	28.921	6	2	0	0
<i>c:</i> 19.38200	<i>D_x:</i> 5.449	29.274	35	2	0	1
<i>Color:</i> Black.		30.365	48	2	0	2
<i>Sample preparation:</i> Prepared by annealing In_2Se_3		32.115	5	2	0	3
<i>(obtained from the elements) in the range 67-770 K.</i>		34.156	7	1	1	5
<i>General comments:</i> γ - In_2Se_3 is the polymorph of In_2Se_3 ,		35.504	5	1	0	7
<i>which is stable at ambient temperature.</i>		37.204	25	2	0	5
<i>Additional pattern:</i> To replace 20-492.		37.547	70	1	1	6
<i>Data collection flag:</i> Ambient.		38.843	41	2	1	1
		39.701	33	2	1	2
		39.943	31	1	0	8
		42.995	7	2	1	4
		43.973	100	3	0	0
		44.231	24	3	0	1
		45.337	28	2	1	5
		47.667	39	2	0	8
		49.403	18	1	1	9
		50.150	5	3	0	5
		51.201	21	2	2	0
		52.696	75	3	0	6
Lutz, H., Universität Siegen, Anorganische Chemie I,		53.275	7	2	2	3
West Germany, Private Communication (1989).		54.547	37	2	1	8
		55.598	8	3	0	7
		56.983	8	0	0	12
		56.983	8	3	1	4
		59.137	13	2	2	6
<i>Radiation:</i> CrK α						
<i>Wavelength:</i> 2.28962						
<i>SS/FOM:</i> F30-55(0.0095, 57)						
<i>Filter:</i> Monochromator crystal						
<i>d-sp:</i> Guinier						
<i>Internal standard:</i> SnO_2						